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Structural health monitoring demonstration of preset-damage microwire arrays enabled composites based on microwave properties

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#ICCM22

Background

➤ Fibre reinforced polymers (FRPs)

Fig.1 A Finnair Airbus A350 using 52% CFRP

Fig.2 First bridge to use CFRP

Fig.3 CFRP blades of Siemens SWT-2.3-101 wind turbines

➤ Columbia Disaster

Fig.4 Accident moment

Fig. 5 The recovered debris of Shuttle Columbia

➤ Structural health monitoring (SHM)

Fibres

- Structural integrity

8-14 μm

- Less size mismatch

Less loading

- Damage sensitivity

SHM for the detection and assessment of such failures is desirable.

Preset-damage microwire arrays enabled composites

➤ Free-standing microwire arrays

Fig. 1 (a) The schematic diagram of waveguide frame (b) Free-standing microwire arrays with preset cracks right on microwires

➤ Microwire array epoxy composites

Fig.2 Microwire array epoxy composites with drilling hole near microwire-A

Free-standing microwire arrays with one crack

Antenna resonance

$$f_{res,n} = \frac{c(2n - 1)}{2l\sqrt{\epsilon}}$$

$$f_A \propto 1/l \rightarrow y$$

$R \propto$ Array periodicity

Fig. 1 (a) The absorption spectra and (b) the reflection spectra of free-standing microwire arrays with one crack.

Surficial modification of microwires by KH550

As the concentration of KH550 increased, the contacting angle between the glass and epoxy decreased, which indicated better surface wettability.

As cast: Epoxy was physically absorbed on the glass

2wt. %: alkoxy group from the silane reacted with hydroxy from the glass

5wt. %: more alkoxy group from the silane reacted with hydroxy from the glass, leading to stronger bonding to the glass

Fig. 1 XPS spectrum for (a) as-prepared glass and glass modified by (b) 2 wt.% and (c) 5 wt.% KH550 silane. Contact angle of (d) as-prepared glass and glass modified by (e) 2 wt.% and (f) 5 wt.% silane to epoxy.

Surficial modification of microwires by KH550

➤ Dual interfaces: 1 Glass/metal core; 2 Glass/epoxy

Fig. 1 Pull-out result for surface-modified microwires embedded by epoxy

Fig. 2 Diagrams and Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images for pulled-out microwires (a) As-cast and modified by (b) 2 wt.% and (c) 5 wt.% silane.

Stress transfer effectiveness: 5wt. % KH550 > 2wt. % KH550 > as cast

Treated microwire array composites with drilling hole

Fig. 1 (a) Transmission and absorption spectra and (b) rate of transmission change composites samples

Microwire modified by 5wt. % KH550 can detect the local 1 mm diameter damage of the order of 1 mm diameter, which is 1 mm away from the nearest microwire in the composite, attributed to tailoring the marked alteration of domain structure after the hole drilling, due to the best improved stress transfer.